

Dreaming – Grounding – Connecting

A self-reflection journey

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This document has been prepared for the 2nd Community Meeting of the Investment
Theme: Transformative bioeconomies: a materials transition that phases out fossil feedstock

More information about the program can be found online:

<http://www.wur.eu/transformative-bioeconomies>

Towards a materials transition
that phases out fossil feedstock

Space to draw your dream.

Connecting

A central aim of the investment theme is to foster inter- and transdisciplinary research. So, we want to know how working together can support the materials transition.

You had a look at **the posters** before, and so you have a rough idea of what others are working on. It would be great to know what your expertise and strengths are that others in the room could profit from.

List and describe up to 3 points.

You also got some sticky notes. Write your 3 offers on three sticky notes and keep them for later!

At times we need to work with others. What **expertise** or other strengths would you love to integrate into your work so that you can make your dream come true? What **partnerships** with other researchers or stakeholders would you love to establish to make your goals come true?

You also got some sticky notes. Write your 3 needs in terms of expertise on three sticky notes and keep them for later.

